

A mental model is the modeling of the debate with the interlocutor

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Annotation: The main issue in this article is about the rational model and its application in social, political economic directions. In general, a rational model is a quick understanding of the state of internal consciousness, which arises under the influence of an external situation that takes place in our thinking without noticing. A rational model can be the basis of individual behavior. It not only affects the external process, but also contributes to the formation of a person's consciousness. With the help of this proverb you will get acquainted with the processes of intelligent modeling.

Keywords: A mental model, internal and external perception, modeling, methodology, human character.

A rational model is the first point that moves thoughts and ideas that arise in the minds of mankind. Therefore, while mankind does not have information about this model, it is something that is unique to everyone. That is, we can call it the concept that arises in the influence of an event or phenomenon.

This is an explanation of someone's thinking process about how something works in the real world.

Mental models are personal, internal images of external reality, which people use to interact with the surrounding world. They are built by people on their own unique life experiences, their imagination and understanding of the world. Rational models are used for thinking and making decisions, and can be the basis of individual behavior. They provide new data filtering and storage mexanizmini. Recognizing and interacting with a multitude of stakeholders ' concepts, values and objectives is currently a key aspect of the practice of effective management of Natural Resources. Therefore, in order to better understand how intelligent models represent complex, dynamic systems internally, and how these images change over time, it allows us to develop effective management and utilization of Natural Resources. However, it is necessary to develop and test appropriate tools and methods to realize this potential, to effectively identify these internal representations of the world.

"You can achieve undeniable personal advantages with the help of a smart model. In this regard, it is necessary to use the principles of logistics to build the main boundaries. It does not require the use of a smart model for personal data other employees in your enterprise/organization have the same business practices as the intelligent modeling methodology. However, you will gain a number of additional advantages 1mulk, if colleagues use approaches, adapting key areas similar to the methodology of intelligent modeling, especially structural principles. In this case, the smart model becomes not only a personal tool for achieving results, but also a tool for achieving the results of the entire department or enterprise. The need to concentrate all the forces on the performance of tasks that lead to forward goals are the tasks / elements that exist in each main field that belong both to the whole enterprise and to the individual enterprise. The list will help you determine the main areas of your organization."

This clever program can differ depending on the character of a person, his gestures and his behavior in the process of conversation. The behavior of a person can not be accidental, because in consciousness a sequence of mental programs is established. Sometimes a person can not reconcile with another interlocutor, because he does not try to model his clever program in his personal circle. According to experts, one person can imagine understanding another interlocutor as modeling his clever program. If in communication the process is accepted according to your mental program, then in your opinion, you can understand your partner.

And or, if we focus our attention not on the inner logic of the interlocutor, but on the fact that what is said is contrary to our inner logic or not, then, as a rule, understanding does not happen. An example for two processes: if the idea with the person you are building a dispute comes out of one place, but the solutions are different, you can understand that person. Here the smart model works directly. If the interlocutor seems incomprehensible from the words of the conversation, then you quickly send a signal to the brain about it and break yourself that you can not talk with him. As already mentioned above, the mental model is a quick understanding of the state of internal consciousness that occurs in the external state, which occurs in our thinking without noticing. In this regard, there is a table on modeling the intelligent program of interlocutors. In the first column, the assumptions that the interlocutors say, and in the second column the commands are set to say exactly the same answers. The third column contains assumptions that are complex in structure. When a person calls another person a nars, he or she tries to influence his or her mind program in this way with the aim of activating commands that can lead to the word or behavior he or she wants.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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